

LASER BASED PRETREATMENT OF ALUMIUM CASTINGS FOR HYBRID INJECTION MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

The necessity to reduce carbon dioxide emissions from motor vehicles to protect the global climate confronts the automotive industry with challenges, particularly in cost-driven large batch production. Vehicle weights are increasing due to higher safety standards, higher demands for comfort and an increasing number of advanced driver assistance systems. On the other hand, the reduction of vehicle weight is one way of producing environmentally friendlier vehicles. In this context, the development of efficient lightweight constructions using innovative ways of production is driven forward. Hybrid construction, which is based on a combination of different materials in order to obtain tailored components with improved properties, is one way to produce innovative lightweight solutions. The combination of plastics and metals to form plastic-metal hybrid components is of particular interest in this investigation. For the production of these components, the hybrid injection molding is one promising approach. This paper therefore examines the in-mold assembly joining of aluminum die castings (AlSi10MnMg) and gravity die castings (AlSi11Mg) with a polyamide 6, which has a 30% glass fibers content. The experiments have shown that a pretreatment of the metallic joining partner is necessary to produce high-strength joints. Furthermore, the influence of a laser pretreatment on the resulting interface in dependence on the used laser power settings is shown and the resulting lap shear strength of the joints will be discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Stricter limit values for carbon dioxide emissions from motor vehicles, climate protection targets and constantly increasing requirements for safety, comfort and driving dynamics in combination with increasing vehicle weight lead to major challenges for the automotive industry [1]. In this context, the development of efficient lightweight constructions suitable for a large batch production is essential. The implementation of this approach requires the use of innovative component production, such as hybrid construction [2].

The combination of plastics and metals to form plastic-metal hybrid components is one way of implementing lightweight constructions. This is the basis for tailored components, in which the properties of the different material classes are used synergistically and are therefore superior to a one material approach [3]. The production of hybrid components can be divided in post-mold assembly (PMA) and in-mold assembly (IMA) [4]. In PMA, the different components are manufactured separately and joined subsequently. In IMA, the metal parts are for example inserted into the injection mold and joined with the injected plastic melt in one step to form a hybrid component [4-6]. With regard to the manufacturing methods, the IMA is further subdivided into the three different process variants insert technology, outsert technology and hybrid technology [3]. Whereas the insert and

outsert technology usually aims at a form-fit and force-fit connection between the components, the aim of hybrid technology is to produce a joint based on adhesive bonding or to apply a combination of adhesive bonding, form-fit and force-fit connections. The adhesive character of the plastic material is used to enable a direct bond between the different components [7, 8].

Comparable to the pretreatment of casting surfaces for adhesive bonding applications, a pretreatment of the cast component for IMA is required to ensure an aging-resistant joint. In the field of metal surface pretreatments for plastic-metal hybrid components, the laser has been in the focus of research for years. It has been shown comprehensively for various metallic components (e.g. DC-01 [9], 1.4301[10, 11], E335 [12], EN AW 1050A [13], EN AW 6082 [14, 15]) that by laser pretreatment high-strength metal-plastic joints can be achieved without additional adhesives.

The PMA (e.g. [9-11, 14, 15]) as process variant was in the main focus of many investigations. So far, the IMA using hybrid injection molding (e.g. [12, 13]) and especially aluminum casting alloys as metallic part has attracted less attention. This paper therefore focuses on the surface pretreatment of aluminum gravity die castings and die castings for an application in IMA with the aim of high-strength joints without the usage of additional materials. Alongside these investigations the influence of different laser power settings on the formation of the surface structures is discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This chapter introduces the used materials, the applied surface pretreatment method, the sample manufacturing process and the testing methods.

2.1 Applied Materials and Test Specimens

For the metallic test specimens, plates made of the aluminum alloys AlSi11Mg (gravity die casting) and AlSi10MnMg (die casting) are produced. The lap-shear specimens with the dimensions 95 mm x 25 mm x 6 mm are then cut out of these plates by water jet. Before the AlSi11Mg samples are used, a heat treatment is applied by annealing the specimens at 540 °C, quenching in water at 60 °C and then artificially aging at 180 °C. In accordance to the typical application fields of die cast parts and to prevent blistering, no preliminary heat treatment on the AlSi10MnMg specimens is done.

The plastic material for the injection molding process is a thermoplastic polyamide 6 with 30% glass fiber content (PA 6 GF 30).

2.2 Surface Pretreatment

The aluminum specimens are pretreated with a nanosecond pulsed fiber laser redENERGY G4 H type from SPI Lasers UK Limited (Southampton, United Kingdom). The samples are cleaned in advance by a wipe degreasing with isopropanol. The applied laser has a wavelength of 1062 ± 2 nm with an average power of 70 W and a pulse peak power of 20 kW at a maximum repetition rate of 1000 kHz.

For the pretreatment, the surface of the samples was processed with separate lines which are orthogonal to the main force direction during lap-shear testing (see Fig. 2). The deflection of the laser beam is realized with an F-Theta lens SS-II-LD-15 from RAYLASE GmbH (Weßling, Germany). By scanning the surface two times at a scanning speed of 1500 mm/s, line structures are only generated in the joining area. The laser power used to produce the line structures is varied between 28 W and 70 W. Fig. 1 shows the ablation process and the parameters used.

Fig. 1: Laser pretreatment process of the aluminum surface and used parameters.

2.3 Sample manufacturing process

The lap-shear test specimens based on DIN EN 1465 are prepared using the IMA approach. The standard length of the overlap had to be reduced from 12.5 mm to 5 mm to prevent a substrate failure of the plastic adherend in subsequent testing. In addition to the aforementioned pretreatment of the aluminum samples, it is also necessary to dry the PA 6 GF 30 granulate used for injection molding before processing to prevent blistering. This becomes necessary due to the water absorption capacity of polyamide 6. To dry the material a vacuum drying oven VD 112 from BINDER GmbH (Tuttlingen, Germany) is used at 80 °C for at least 12 hours. After drying, the PA 6 GF 30 is injection molded onto the aluminum adherends using a victory 330/120 spex injection molding machine from ENGEL AUSTRIA GmbH (Schwertberg, Austria). After manufacturing, the plastic adherends have a dimension of 95 mm x 25 mm x 4 mm.

Before the injection molding process is started, the aluminum adherends are manually positioned in the mold. In order to prevent a rapid cooling of the injected material at the interface the aluminum part needs to be preheated in the mold. Therefore the mold is equipped with heating cartridges on one side and an infrared field on the other side. This preheating is necessary to allow a sufficient wetting of the aluminum surface during the injection molding process. If the preheating temperature is too low, the pretreatment method described in Chapter 2.2 cannot be used to generate adhesion or the connection is of poor quality. The determination of the correct time-temperature process window is therefore decisive for the quality of the joint [see 12]. Preliminary tests have shown that a surface temperature of the aluminum adherend of 220 °C during the mold filling leads to joints with high quality. Fig. 2 shows the test setup on the injection molding machine.

Fig. 2: Simplified visualization of injection molding setup (left) and specimens (right).

The injection molding parameters are listed in table 1. To enable the comparison of different pretreatment settings the injection molding and pre-heating parameters were kept constant for all specimens.

Injection pressure (MPa)	Injection speed (cm ³ /s)	Melt temperature (°C)	Insert temperature at first contact with the melt (°C)	Holding pressure (MPa)
50	20	275	220	25

Table 1: Injection molding parameters used for test series.

2.4 Testing Method

The FEM Quanta FEG 650 scanning electron microscope (SEM) from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. (Waltham, USA) is used to characterize the surface properties of the AlSi11Mg and AlSi10MnMg samples before and after laser surface pretreatment. The secondary electron detector is an Everhart-Thornley-Detector from Thermo Fischer Scientific Inc. (Waltham, USA). The acceleration voltage for all SEM measurements was kept constant at 10 kV. For further evaluation of the laser-structured area, microsections are examined with the AxioImager m2m reflected light microscope from Carl Zeiss AG (Oberkochen, Germany).

The destructive test to determine the lap-shear strength is carried out based on DIN EN 1465 with a Z050 AllroundLine testing machine from ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG (Ulm, Germany) at a testing speed of 10 mm/min. Before testing the specimens are conditioned in accordance with DIN EN ISO 1110 at 70 °C and 62% relative humidity for 7 days in a climatic chamber KBF 720 from BINDER GmbH (Tuttlingen, Germany).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the results of a laser pretreatment of the aluminum casting specimens are presented before the results of the lap-shear tests are discussed.

3.1 Surface pretreatment by laser

The surface of the specimens is pretreated according to the method described in Chapter 2.2. By varying the average laser output power, different surface structures are created. Fig. 3a shows an untreated surface of a gravity die casting sample (AlSi11Mg). Fig. 4a shows a die casting sample (AlSi10MnMg). In both cases the surface has no to very small surface structures, which are the results of the two casting processes.

Fig. 3b to 3d show selected surfaces of the AlSi11Mg alloy after a laser pretreatment. In Fig. 3b, the surface was pretreated with laser parameter 6 (LP 6) which stands for an average laser output power of 35 W. The SEM image shows that the surface was only slightly remelted by this pretreatment setting. The pretreatment also did not cover the entire surface, as untreated areas remain between each pretreatment line. The low extent of the pretreatment can be attributed to the low average output power at which the heat input is insufficient to melt the oxide layer of the aluminum (melting point Al₂O₃: 2050 °C [16]) over the entire surface of the specimen. One reason for this may be the typical intensity distribution of a Gaussian beam profile which results in an ablation threshold [17] on the edges of a pretreatment line.

Especially in the peripheral areas of the focus point, the intensity is below the ablation threshold, resulting in a reduction of the ablation width for the pretreatment of AlSi11Mg. Thus no or only a slight structuring of the surface is achieved with insufficient energy fluence. Another reason for the partial pretreatment can be the hatch distance of 120 µm with a spot diameter of 100 µm. However, if the treatment condition is compared with Fig. 3d, it can be seen that the energy input has a greater influence in this case. At 70 W average output power (Fig. 3d), energy fluence is high enough to melt the aluminum surface in the whole irradiation regime of the spot. The occurring vaporization process and the high recoil pressure of the ablation plume on the surface expel the liquid material resulting in

cavities with ramifications, melt droplets and undercuts at the edges. Because of the range of these ejections a greater surface area is reshaped than the laser actually irradiates. Fig. 3c (56 W laser power) also shows a structured surface, but in this case the lines are still separated. As a result of this separation, additional undercuts are created for the anchoring of the plastic melt.

Fig. 3: SEM images of pretreated AlSi11Mg gravity die casting surface:
a: untreated; b: LP 6; c: LP 3; d: LP 1; u.a.: untreated area.

The pretreatment of the aluminum die cast surfaces (Fig. 4) show a lower ablation threshold when compared to the same settings on gravity die casted surfaces (Fig. 3). Already at a power of 35 W (Fig. 4b) a coarser structuring of the die cast surface can be observed compared to the surface of the gravity die cast parts (Fig. 3b). All further investigated pretreatment intensities also show these differences. The underlying effects of the pretreatment did not change for the material which leads to the assumption, that the gravity die casted aluminum needs lower pretreatment intensities in order to achieve a structured surface. This can result in faster pretreatment processes.

Fig. 4: SEM images of pretreated AlSi10MnMg die casting surface:
a: untreated; b: LP 6; c: LP 3; d: LP 1; u.a.: untreated area.

The microsections of the pretreated surfaces in Fig. 5 also show the different surfaces depending on the applied laser power. Fig. 5a shows the microsection of AlSi11Mg after a pretreatment with 35 W average output power. Similar to the SEM image (Fig. 3a), no structuring is visible. Some areas show structures of 1 µm depth. Due to the low impact of this pretreatment setting it cannot be distinguished if the surface structure originates from the manufacturing process or the laser pretreatment. With increasing processing intensity, the structures become more visible and deeper as there was enough material in the molten state to be ejected by the recoil pressure during irradiation. For LP 3 (Fig. 5b) the structures are 12 µm in depth but the pretreatment lines are still separated which can also be observed in the corresponding SEM image (Fig. 3c). For LP 1 (Fig. 5c) the resulting structure depth can be increased to 17 µm and the untreated areas are fully covered with remelted material. In contrast to this, the corresponding SEM image (Fig. 3d) shows a completely remelted surface. This leads to the assumption, that the recoil pressure results in a heat affect zone which seems to be pretreated completely when viewing from the top view.

The microsections of the die cast components show comparable dependencies as those of the gravity die cast components. However, the surface structuring at LP 6 (Fig. 5d) is already 4 µm deep and therefore more visible compared to the structuring in Fig. 5a. Furthermore, the structures resulting from the pretreatment with LP 3, depicted in Fig. 5e, are deeper (16 µm) than the ones of the

comparable gravity die casting settings. Structures on AlSi10MnMg resulting from LP 1 are 20 μm deep which is 17.6% deeper than the structures on AlSi11Mg. The surface analysis shows that the examined aluminum die casting alloy needs lower pretreatment intensities to achieve comparable results to the examined aluminum gravity casting alloy. After the discussion of the surface analysis the laser pretreatment settings are tested with the lap shear test to determine the influence of the surface structure on the achievable joint strength.

Fig. 5: Microsections of one line structure of pretreated AlSi11Mg gravity die casting surface: a: LP 6; b: LP 3; c: LP 1 and of pretreated AlSi10MnMg die casting surface: d: LP 6; e: LP 3; f: LP 1; u.a.: untreated area; e.m.: ejected material.

3.2 Lap-shear tests

Fig. 6 shows the lap-shear strength of the laser-structured and with the IMA manufactured aluminum-cast plastic hybrids. The highest lap-shear strength of 40.97 ± 3.57 MPa is achieved with the connection between AlSi10MnMg and PA 6 GF 30 using the pretreatment parameter LP 1. For the other laser parameters, the strength varies between 0.42 ± 1.02 MPa (LP 6) and 36.7 ± 3.99 MPa (LP 3) depending on the average laser power used for the surface pretreatment. In comparison the highest joint strength of the AlSi11Mg-PA 6 GF 30 hybrids is 31% lower at 28.21 ± 3.15 MPa (LP 3). Here, as well, the dependence on the amount of surface structuring induced by the intensity of laser radiation is shown by the fact that the strengths vary between 0.62 ± 1.52 MPa (LP 6) and 36.7 ± 3.99 MPa (LP 3).

The necessity of a pretreatment is clarified by the fact that no joining between either materials could be achieved without a pretreatment. For the pretreatment parameter LP 6, it can be seen for both materials that the low structuring of the surface, as can be seen in Fig. 3a and 4a, leads only to low strengths. The lap-shear specimens pre-treated with LP 6 also show adhesive failure (AF) in 5 out of 6 samples and substrate cohesive failure (SCF) only in one sample. With increasing laser power up to laser parameter LP 4, the joint strengths of both materials increase but show a high standard deviation. In addition, the failure mode changes from LP 5 to AF for all specimens. From LP 3 onwards, an increase in strength with a simultaneous decrease in standard deviation can be observed. For the connections between AlSi10MnMg and PA 6 GF 30, the strength increases from LP 4 (16.51 ± 7.71 MPa) to LP 3 (36.7 ± 3.99 MPa) by 122%, for the AlSi11Mg-PA 6 GF 30 connections from LP 4 (15.26 ± 7.23 MPa) to LP 3 (28.21 ± 3.15 MPa) by 86%.

Fig. 6: Results of lap-shear tests.

Considering the SEM images and microsections, it can be stated that there is a threshold for the intensity of the laser pretreatment which results in high-strength connections when exceeded. For both investigated materials, the threshold is 80% (56 W) average laser power. Furthermore, the results indicate that despite a similar surface structure, the maximum possible strengths also depends on the aluminum adherend or the casting process used or both. The surface structuring on the AISi10MnMg specimens as a result of processing with LP 1 is 17.64% deeper than on the AISi11Mg specimens. In comparison to that, 122% higher strengths could be achieved with the AISi10MnMg specimens. Compared to [18], the strength of 40.97 ± 3.57 MPa in IMA with laser-structured metals and a PA 6 GF30 are up to 350% higher. In [9] lap-shear specimens were investigated using PMA with laser-structured steel [DC01] and thermoplastic glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6. Compared to [9], the maximum strengths of the present paper are about 35% higher.

3 CONCLUSION

In this paper, die cast (AISI10MnMg) and gravity die cast (AISI11Mg) parts were pretreated by laser for the use in a hybrid injection molding processes with different parameters. The introduced process can achieve high strength joints between both aluminum alloys and a PA 6 GF 30. In this context, it was shown that the results of the surface pretreatment depend on applied laser power. A threshold value of 56 W (80%) average laser power of the 1064 nm fiber laser used (max. 70 W average laser power) provided an increase in strength of 122% and an almost complete surface structuring showing a heat affect zone. For joints between AISi10MnMg and PA 6 GF 30 40.97 ± 3.57 MPa, for AISi11Mg-PA 6 GF 30 28.21 ± 3.15 MPa were determined as maximum strengths. This corresponds to a strength increase of 45.2% of the die cast specimen compared to the gravity die cast samples. In contrast, the structures of the die cast specimens were only 17.64% deeper, which indicates a dependence on the material of the joining partner or on the casting process used or both. The interdependence of the material and the casting process on the resulting joint strength should therefore be the subject of following investigations. The existence of the threshold value for the required laser intensity should be verified in further investigations with other laser systems in order to make a general statement about the required laser power.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Dilger, Demokratisierter Leichtbau, *Jahrbuch 2014 der Braunschweigischen Wissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft*, Cramer, pp.75-84, 2015.
- [2] F. Henning and E. Moeller (Ed.), *Handbuch Leichtbau. Methoden, Werkstoffe, Fertigung*, Carl Hanser Verlag München Wien, München, 2011.
- [3] H. Ridders and J. Schnieders, Hybridspritzgießen - Möglichkeiten und Grenze, *Proceedings of Tagung Spritzgießen 2007, Baden-Baden, Germany,, February 14-5,2007*, VDI-Verlag, Düsseldorf, 2007.
- [4] U. Endemann, S. Glaser and M. Völker, Verbindungstechnik für Kunststoff-Metall-Hybridstrukturen: Kunststoff und Metall im festen Verbund, *Kunststoffe*, vol. 92, issue 11, pp. 110-113, 2002.
- [5] H. Goldach and J. Hoffner, Hybridbauteil in der Serienfertigung, *Anwendungstechnische Information*, Bayer Leverkusen AG, pp. 1-5, 2000.
- [6] M. Op de Laak, G. Pötsch, K.Schwitzter, Kunststoff-Metall-Hybrid, *Kunststoffe*, vol. 9, issue 9, pp. 112-118, 2001.
- [7] H. Paul, M. Luke and F. Henning Kunststoff-Metall-Hybridverbunde - Experimentelle Untersuchungen zum Verformungs- und Versagensverhalten, *Kunststofftechnik - Journal of plastics technology*, vol. 10, issue 4, pp.117-141, 2014.
- [8] M. Grujicic, V. Sellappan, M.A. Omar, N.Seyer, A. Obieglo, M. Erdmann and J. Holzleitner, An overview of the polymer-to-metal direct adhesion hybrid technologies for load-bearing automotive components, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 197, pp. 363–373, 2008.
- [9] K. Lippky, M. Mund, D. Blass and K.Dilger, Investigation of hybrid fusion bonds under varying manufacturing and operating procedures, *Composite Structures*, vol. 202, pp. 275–282, 2018.
- [10] J. Eckstädt and J. Rauschenberger, Laser joining of textured metal and plastic component, *Proceedings of Laser in Manufacturing Conference 2017, (Eds.L. Overmeyer, U. Reisgen, A-Ostendorf, M. Schmidt)München, Germany, June 26-29,2017*, München, 2017, pp. 1-11.
- [11] A. Roesner, S. Scheik, A. Olowinsky, A. Gillner, U. Reisgen, and M. Schleser, Laser Assisted Joining of Plastic Metal Hybrids, *Physics Procedia*, vol 12, pp. 370.377, 2011.
- [12] D. Spancken, K. van der Straeten, J. Beck and N. Stötzner, Laserstrukturierung von Metalloberflächen für Hybridverbindungen, *Lightweight Design*, vol. 11, issue 4, pp 16–23, 2018.
- [13] P. Amend, M. Wolf, T. Mrotzek, T. Laumer, S. Roth, M. Gude and M. Schmidt, Experimental investigations on laser-based hot-melt bonding and injection molding for laser-structured metal plastic hybrids, *Proceedings of Laser in Manufacturing Conference 2017;(Eds.L. Overmeyer, U. Reisgen, A- Ostendorf, M. Schmidt), München, Germany, June 26-29,2017*, München, 2017, pp. 1-7.
- [14] K. Schricker, M. Stambke, J. P. Bergmann, Jean Pierre and K. Bräutigam, Laser-Based Joining of Thermoplastics to Metals: Influence of Varied Ambient Conditions on Joint Performance and Microstructure, *International Journal of Polymer Science*, vol. 2016, pp 1-9, 2016.
- [15] A. Heckert, C. Singer, M. F. Zaeh, R. Daub and T. Zeilinger, Gas-tight thermally joined metal-thermoplastic connections by pulsed laser surface pre-treatment, *Proceedings of 9th International Conference on Photonic Technologies - LANE 2016, (Eds. M. Schmidt, F. Vollertsen, C. B. Arnold), Fürth, Germany, September 19-22, 2016*, vol. 83, pp. 1083-1093, 2016.
- [16] F. Ostermann , *Anwendungstechnologie Aluminium*, Springer Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, 2014
- [17] D. Müller, B. Klimt, H. Haloui *Mikrobearbeitung mit Pikosekunden-Lasersystemen: Qualität, Kosten und Zuverlässigkeit*. Proceedings of 7. Jenaer Lasertagung. DVS-Berichte Bd.271, pp. 165-172, DVS-Verlag, Düsseldorf, 2010